

Tourism Potencies Identification on Local's New-Born Activities towards Pandemic COVID-19 Resilience in Bongkasa Pertiwi Village, Bali-Indonesia

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Abstract

This paper identifies the tourism potential that exists in new-born local activities in dealing with the resilience of the COVID-19 pandemic in Bongkasa Pertiwi Village. This Village is known by tourists as a nature-based tourism, with cultural tourism as its support. However, a pandemic tore apart Bongkasa Pertiwi Villagers' lives who live from Tourism sector as source income, and it led to a crisis. This study aims to identify existing and new-born activities by villagers and analyze their emergence to see tourism potential that can be developed in this pandemic condition. Researchers collect data and information by field surveys to the location of Bongkasa Pertiwi Village in Badung Regency, as well as interview resource persons consisting of village officials and the locals, especially those who created new activities. The results are analyzed by using case study methods and qualitative approaches while considering SIT motives as tools to complement qualitative approaches in this identification. Based on analysis, several local new-born activities can be optimized for tourism potential as resilience to face the pandemic. No matter how small, it becomes a good opportunity to be developed into an interesting tourism activity. The crisis and pandemic did not undermine the enthusiasm of Bongkasa Pertiwi Villagers to provide people's needs for tourism even when the Pandemic was over.

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1. Introduction

Tourism sector is the biggest source of income for Bali province, as Statistical Data of Tourists visits to Bali in recent 4 years (2016-2019) show an upward trend in tourist visits (Pariwisata, 2019). Tourism sector is able to create millions of jobs for local people, whether through direct work in tourism facilities, selling items, or services. Bongkasa Pertiwi Village also gets the shared profit of those uptrends in tourists visiting. Bongkasa Pertiwi Village is one of the “Desa Wisata” (Tourism Villages) according to Badung Regent Regulations No. 47 year 2010 about establishment of Desa Wisata Area in Badung Regency (Pemerintah Daerah Badung, 2010)

Before the Pandemic, Bongkasa Pertiwi Village was well-known as a provider of natural and cultural tourism among tourists, especially from Australia, China, and USA. Many tourists visit to enjoy or experience tourism activities that have been provided in Bongkasa Pertiwi Village. One of the most popular tourism activities or destinations in Bongkasa Pertiwi Village is “Bali Swing”. Unfortunately, the Bali Swing destination was closed for a long period because of this Pandemic. It also has a negative impact on other tourism activities, such as decrease in sales of local merchandise, and of course the greatest impact is on villager’s welfare. According to UNWTO, there are 5 (five) factors that influence the recovery of tourism or travel sectors, such as: 1) Travel restrictions regulations; 2) Slow-virus containment; 3) lack of responses among countries; 4) low customer’s self-confidence; 5) indecisive flight re-opening (Gegung, 2021).

Figure 1. Factors that Weighing on The Recovery of International Tourism

Source : <http://www.unwto.org/impact-assessment-of-the-covid-19-outbreak-on-international-tourism>, (accessed 10 October 2021)

The conditions led to an indecisive back to normal - period regarding the Bongkasa Pertiwi Village’s tourism as well as its wealth for the local people. However, The term ‘Resilience’ might be already in Bongkasa Pertiwi Villager’s mindset during this Pandemic, thus, humans have the ability to learn from previous experience and generalize those learned lessons to create a solution or problem solver sporadically (Litman, 2021).

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Bongkasa Pertiwi Village

Bongkasa Pertiwi village is located in Abiansemal District, Badung Regency, at an altitude of less than 500 above sea level (not a coastal area). Based on the Decree of the Regent of Badung No. 1067 of 2003, this village is derived from the division of Bongkasa Village, within an area about 1.56 Km². Bongkasa Pertiwi Village area is surrounded by Desa Carangsari (north), Ayung River in Kedewatan Village (east), Bongkasa Village (south), and Taman Village (west). It takes 45-50 minutes to travel from Denpasar City, or 1 hour 9 minutes from Ngurah Rai Airport to Bongkasa Pertiwi village.

Source :

<https://www.google.com/maps/place/Bongkasa+Pertiwi,+Kec.+Abiansemal,+Kabupate+n+Badung,+Bali>, (accessed on 10th October 2021)

Bongkasa Pertiwi Village consists of three sub-villages (banjar). The first one is Banjar Tegal Kuning which has a rafting attraction on Ayung River, in addition to massage and spa service. The second Banjar called Banjar Karang Dalem 2 with silver handicraft as the main source of income. Thirdly, Banjar Karang Dalem 1, has a panoramic view of the numerous rice terraces of subak. The distance between the houses is very far as they are scattered by the rice field.

Source :

<https://www.google.com/maps/place/Bongkasa+Pertiwi,+Kec.+Abiansemal,+Kabupate+n+Badung,+Bali>, (accessed on 10th October 2021)

Bongkasa Pertiwi as a Tourism Village

Bongkasa Village is one of the tourism villages in Bali that relies on the preservation and utilization of landscapes and community culture as the attraction for tourist visits. Therefore, the beautiful natural scenery of the countryside becomes a potential attraction for the tourists provided by the villagers. As an illustration, there is a meandering flow of the Ayung River stretching from upstream to downstream like a big dragon and agricultural landscapes ranging from rice fields. In terms of farming activities, the farmers create huts for their shelter and at the same time use them for raising their livestock and herd them around offering natural tourist attractions.

Meanwhile, the village offers cultural potential in both tangible and intangible aspects. In the Tangible aspect, Bongkasa Pertiwi Village has Balinese architecture presented in their traditional houses. Another unique thing, Batu Megong, situated at the Subak Temple, would be a cultural symbol that can only be witnessed in Bongkasa village. Moreover several products also produced by the villagers related to their crafting as well as cuisine skill. On the other hand, the intangible aspects can be seen from daily activities of farmers working in the fields accompanied by the religious ritual activities in the rice fields, Bedugul, Subak Temple, or Kahyangan Tiga Temple as tourist attractions.

Besides those cultural activities mentioned above, man-made attractions are also created as a response to the existence of natural and cultural tourism potential in the Bongkasa Pertiwi Village. Those attractions include Bali Swing, Pinball, and ATV as well as a silver craft center. There are 26 Tourism Activities available in Bongkasa Pertiwi Village, the categories and types of services are described as follows:

Table 1. Current Tourism Activities available in Bongkasa Pertiwi Village

No	Object/Activities	Type Of Services	Tourism Activity Categories	Location
1	Bali Swing	Tourist Rides	Man-made Attraction	Br. Tegal Kuning
2	Sky Swing Bali	Tourist Rides	Man-made Attraction	Br. Karang Dalem I
3	Pertiwi Quad Adventure	Rafting	Man-made Attraction	Br. Karang Dalem I
4	Yellow Garden Rafting	Rafting	Man-made Attraction	Br. Tegal Kuning
5	Paintball Bali Pertiwi	Shooting	Man-made Attraction	Br. Karang Dalem I
6	Buk Dita/ Desak Nyoman Murtini	Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism	Br. Karang Dalem I, Desa Bongkasa Pertiwi
7	Men Ranik/Ni Made Indrayani	Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism	Br. Tegal Kuning, Desa Bongkasa Pertiwi
8	Mek Osin/Ni Wayan Wardani	Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism	Br. Tegal Kuning, Desa Bongkasa Pertiwi

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9	Agung Nyoman/ I Gst. Ag. Ayu Nyoman	Porridge	Culinary Tourism	Br. Karang Dalem I, Desa Bongkasa Pertiwi
10	Mek Armini/Ni Wayan Armini	Porridge	Culinary Tourism	Br. Tegal Kuning, Desa Bongkasa Pertiwi
11	Mek Anik/Ni Ketut Nami	Porridge and Traditional Snacks (<i>Laklak</i>)	Culinary Tourism	Br. Tegal Kuning, Desa Bongkasa Pertiwi
12	Men Rai/Ni Made Lodri	Porridge and Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism	Br. Tegal Kuning, Desa Bongkasa Pertiwi
13	Anak Agung Maha Laksmi Dewi	Traditional Snacks (<i>Godoh</i> /Fried Banana)	Culinary Tourism	Br. Tegal Kuning, Desa Bongkasa Pertiwi
14	Buk Sika/Ni Wayan Rimin	Culinary	Culinary Tourism	Br. Tegal Kuning, Desa Bongkasa Pertiwi
15	Airy Ubud Dewi Saraswati	Villa	Lodging	Jalan Dewi Saraswati, Karang Dalem I
16	Candra Loka Villa	Villa	Lodging	Jalan Dewi Gangga, Karang Dalem Ii
17	Amara Giri Villa	Villa	Lodging	Jalan Dewi Saraswati
18	Nalar House Jungle View	Villa	Lodging	Jalan Dewi Saraswati
19	Pondok Mesari	Villa	Lodging	Jalan Dewi Saraswati
20	Pramana Private House Rice Field View	Villa	Lodging	Jalan Dewi Saraswati
21	Villa Manis 2 Bedroom Private Pool View	Villa	Lodging	Jalan Dewi Saraswati
22	Pupuk Cair Wanita Tani "Manik Pertiwi" (Liquid Fertilizer)	Farming	Agrotourism	-
23	Pupuk Kompos Wanita Tani "Manik Pertiwi" (Compost)	Farming	Agrotourism	-
24	Ngaben Massal Ceremony	Cultural	Cultural Tourism	Br. Karang Dalem I
25	Silver Class By Pak Melan	Private Lessons	Cultural Tourism	Br. Karang Dalem II,
26	Sri Rahayu Silver	silver craft	Artshop	Br. Karang Dalem II

Figure 4. Bongkasa Pertiwi Village Tourism Activities

Source :

<https://www.google.com/maps/place/Bongkasa+Pertiwi,+Kec.+Abiansemal,+Kabupaten+Badung,+Bali> , (accessed on 10th October 2021)

Resilience

The word Resilience is derived from “*resilire*” then experience a word formation into “*resilience*” which is commonly understood as capacity-building ability, an ability to rebound from adverse events, or a capacity of a system so the system can absorb problems and reorganize it while also making changes so as to essentially retain the same function, structure, identity and feedbacks (Adams, et al., 2021). Resilience is also known as the capacity for transformation and adaptation in the face of change (Rescia et al., 2010, #). The changes that occur tend to be caused by crises that are performed at various spatial scales. This understanding aims to prepare for pre-disaster conditions, post-disaster recovery, and estimate potential losses (Frazier et al., 2013, #). In terms of Tourism studies, resilience is often referred to the intuitive appeal from a community to meet immediate life-saving and sustainable life needs. Currently, Covid-19 Pandemic is categorized as force majeure disaster in Indonesia. This disaster has created changes in various aspects of life particularly in the restricted travel activities. These restrictions had led to economic activity in Bali, which is driven by the tourism sector, undergoing a significant financial crisis.

According to Rutger Bregman in *Humankind* (2020), psychologically, the crisis does cause a temporary deep sadness or anger. Afterward, the community has a tendency to be resistant in facing crises similar to what happened with the Bongkasa Pertiwi Villagers. It can be seen from the numerous new activities emerging in the pandemic era. These new-born activities are becoming the manifestation of community resilience during facing the crises because of pandemic. The primary problem discussed in this study is related to finding the models of resilience practices employed by a tourism village (community) that has had activated tourism activities before the pandemic. Later, there is a big hope that with the results of this study, the condition could be recovered in a short time by directly solving the problems that the locals faced. Based on this explanation, it is necessary to identify new activities that have emerged since the pandemic took place. In addition potential mapping of the new-born activities would be created to help the resilience process meet the

expectation to increase the welfare of Bongkasa Pertiwi Villager. At the end, Policies will be drawn up by targeting existing tourism activity and new-born tourism activity points that emerged as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic

2. Materials and Methods

This research uses a qualitative approach through employing case study research methods, where researchers began by collecting data through survey, direct interview, observation, and activities participation around the village. It is aimed at studying the conditions of existing tourism destinations and new emerging activities during pandemic COVID-19. Researchers were also collecting manuscript data such as government regulations, village regulations, and other documents that related to minimizing the effect of pandemic. After collecting data, it is analyzed through identification and comparison regarding which one was the new emerging activities by local and which one was the existing activities. All data are also accompanied by detailed reasons why the new activities emerge and its relation to pandemic impact on previous activities while considering SIT motives as tools to complement qualitative approaches in this identification. The results of this identification would be proposed as new-born tourism activities and also economic opportunities as manifestation of Bongkasa Pertiwi Village resilience in facing the crisis during pandemic.

3. Results and Discussions

Researchers found a lot of information as the primary and secondary data. The data is processed and analyzed, then resulted in 3 (three) main points as follows.

3.1 Local New-born Activities : Tourism Activities During Pandemic and After Pandemic

The COVID-19 pandemic has had an impact on tourism activities in Bongkasa Pertiwi Village. Bongkasa Pertiwi Village is included in 11 (eleven) Tourism Villages in Badung Regency. In this village, man-made attractions have become one of the most popular categories chosen by the visitors. Those activities are Bali Swing, ATV Ride, Rafting, Paintball, and Quad Adventure. These attractions provide many job opportunities that can be filled by the community. It makes the welfare of the community of Bongkasa Pertiwi Village quite decent. However once the pandemic began to strike in March 2020, it led to the enactment of a travel ban (travel warning), which caused tourist visits to Bongkasa Pertiwi Village drop immediately. This situation became worse by a dramatic decrease in the occupancy rate of overnight stays of tourists in Ubud, the area where mostly Bongkasa Pertiwi villagers work for living.

Table 2. Current Condition of Tourism Object in Bongkasa Pertiwi Village

No	Object/Activities	Type Of Services	Tourism Activity Categories	Status
1	Bali Swing	Tourist Rides	Man-made Attraction	Closed
2	Sky Swing Bali	Tourist Rides	Man-made Attraction	Closed
3	Pertiwi Quad Adventure	Rafting	Man-made Attraction	Closed

4	Yellow Garden Rafting	Rafting	Man-made Attraction	Closed
5	Paintball Bali Pertiwi	Shooting	Man-made Attraction	Closed
6	Buk Dita/ Desak Nyoman Murtini	Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
7	Men Ranik/Ni Made Indrayani	Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
8	Mek Osin/Ni Wayan Wardani	Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
9	Agung Nyoman/ I Gst. Ag. Ayu Nyoman	Porridge	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
10	Mek Armini/Ni Wayan Armini	Porridge	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
11	Mek Anik/Ni Ketut Nami	Porridge and Traditional Snacks (<i>Laklak</i>)	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
12	Men Rai/Ni Made Lodri	Porridge and Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
13	Anak Agung Maha Laksmi Dewi	Traditional Snacks (<i>Godoh</i> /Fried Banana)	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
14	Buk Sika/Ni Wayan Rimin	Culinary	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
15	Airy Ubud Dewi Saraswati	Villa	Lodging	Low Occupancy
16	Candra Loka Villa	Villa	Lodging	Low Occupancy
17	Amara Giri Villa	Villa	Lodging	Low Occupancy
18	Nalar House Jungle View	Villa	Lodging	Low Occupancy
19	Pondok Mesari	Villa	Lodging	Low Occupancy
20	Pramana Private House Rice Field View	Villa	Lodging	Low Occupancy
21	Villa Manis 2 Bedroom Private Pool View	Villa	Lodging	Low Occupancy
22	Pupuk Cair Wanita Tani "Manik Pertiwi" (Liquid Fertilizer)	Farming	Agrotourism	Open
23	Pupuk Kompos Wanita Tani "Manik Pertiwi (Compost)	Farming	Agrotourism	Open
24	Ngaben Massal Ceremony	Cultural	Cultural Tourism	no visitor
25	Silver Class By Pak Melan	Private Lessons	Cultural Tourism	no visitor
26	Sri Rahayu Silver	silver craft	Artshop	no visitor

Based on the activities identification in table 2, many man-made tourism activities, which were created for tourists' convenience, are closed. Because of the low number of visits, many residents who previously worked on these attractions ended up changing their jobs or even being unemployed. This Condition seems to be very detrimental to residents because it reduces their income which affects the ability to meet their daily needs. People are trying to find business opportunities that are still possible to do. This condition makes people begin to think of other ways to support their family's life. They are starting to see opportunities not only foreign visitors but also for providing service for local people. Therefore many residents choose to change jobs, in order to earn money to support their families. Several new-born activities due to pandemic conditions can be seen as follows.

Table 3. New-born Activities

No	Object/Activities	Type Of Services	Tourism Activity Categories	Status
1	Bali Swing	Tourist Rides	Man-made Attraction	Closed
2	Sky Swing Bali	Tourist Rides	Man-made Attraction	Closed
3	Pertiwi Quad Adventure	Rafting	Man-made Attraction	Closed
4	Yellow Garden Rafting	Rafting	Man-made Attraction	Closed
5	Paintball Bali Pertiwi	Shooting	Man-made Attraction	Closed
6	Buk Dita/ Desak Nyoman Murtini	Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
7	Men Ranik/Ni Made Indrayani	Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
8	Mek Osin/Ni Wayan Wardani	Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
9	Anak Agung Maha Laksmi Dewi	Traditional Snacks (Godoh/Fried Banana)	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
10	Men Devi/ Ni Made Kariyanti	Culinary Tourism	Culinary Tourism	Newly Emerged (new-born)
11	Agung Nyoman/ I Gst. Ag. Ayu Nyoman	Porridge	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
12	Mek Armini/Ni Wayan Armini	Porridge	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
13	Men Rai/Ni Made Lodri	Porridge and Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
14	Men Saren/Ni Nyoman Sri Adnyani	Porridge and Traditional Snacks		Newly Emerged (new-born)

15	Men Pina/Ni Ketut Aryani	Porridge and Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism	Newly Emerged (new-born)
16	Mek Anik/Ni Ketut Nami	Porridge and Traditional Snacks (<i>Laklak</i>)	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
17	Men Tawa/ Ni Nyoman Artini	Porridge and Traditional Snacks (<i>Laklak</i>)	Culinary Tourism	Newly Emerged (new-born)
18	Dong Sangklib/Ni Made Tomog	Porridge and Traditional Snacks (<i>Laklak</i>)	Culinary Tourism	Newly Emerged (new-born)
19	Buk Sika/Ni Wayan Rimin	Culinary	Culinary Tourism	local consumers only
20	Airy Ubud Dewi Saraswati	Villa	Lodging	Low Occupancy
21	Candra Loka Villa	Villa	Lodging	Low Occupancy
22	Amara Giri Villa	Villa	Lodging	Low Occupancy
23	Nalar House Jungle View	Villa	Lodging	Low Occupancy
24	Pondok Mesari	Villa	Lodging	Low Occupancy
25	Pramana Private House Rice Field View	Villa	Lodging	Low Occupancy
26	Villa Manis 2 Bedroom Private Pool View	Villa	Lodging	Low Occupancy
27	Pupuk Cair Wanita Tani "Manik Pertiwi" (Liquid Fertilizer)	Farming	Agrotourism	Open
28	Pupuk Kompos Wanita Tani "Manik Pertiwi" (Compost)	Farming	Agrotourism	Open
29	Honey Farmer Kele-Kele Sarining Trigona Pertiwi	Farming/Livestock	Agrotourism	Newly Emerged (new-born)
30	Ngaben Massal Ceremony	Cultural	Cultural Tourism	no visitor
31	Silver Class By Pak Melan	Private Lessons	Cultural Tourism	no visitor
32	Sri Rahayu Silver	silver craft	Artshop	no visitor
33	Kerajinan Tas Daur Ulang Eco Pertiwi	Eco-handcraft	Recycle Product	Newly Emerged (new-born)
34	Bank Sampah Yellow Garden	Pengumpul Sampah	Lingkungan	Newly Emerged (new-born)

The community has begun to develop their business in the field of food security within heterogeneous targets, both local people and visitors. The one who has sufficient financial capital, they develop livestock business or farming, such as pig, cow, or honey bee farms. Meanwhile, the one who has cooking skills will tend to open a culinary business. In addition, the community has also begun to focus on environmental preservation, through utilizing plastic waste into daily use craft,

like tote bags, sandals, and other crafts. In other words, culinary activities dominated the type of new-born activities in this village.

1.2. Identifying New-born Activities as Tourism Potencies in Resilience during the Pandemic

Resilience can be distinguished by four different types : 1) Resilience as resistance; 2) Resilience as bounceback; 3) Resilience as an adaptation; 4) Resilience as a transformation (Era & Rosario, 2020, #).

Although the existence of tourism is now considered uncertain, efforts to increase visits from outsiders to villages are also still being strengthened. This increase in visits is solely to rotate the economic movement in the village. The new-born activities in Bongkasa Pertiwi village which develop during the pandemic. Based on the results of the existing data, local activities that persist are activities that accommodate basic needs (such as food/culinary) or tourist attractions that utilize natural resources as an attraction. That means, indirectly, it is explained that sustainable tourism is tourism that lives with nature and makes nature a necessity so that it must be maintained. Sustainable tourism activities are balanced. In the pre-disaster period, the profit may not be more than man-made tourism. However, when a pandemic occurs, the conditions will remain stable and may even increase due to available business opportunities. The community can also set aside and provide a place for the preservation of natural resources when conducting tourism activities. During this pandemic, the most effective sources of life for development are agriculture and culinary.

Bongkasa Pertiwi village has other potential villages that can be combined with local's new-born activities to be developed into tourist attractions. The natural atmosphere and village activities on a calm morning have the potential to become a jogging track and cycling route. This offer is based on trends of increasing interest of cyclists during the pandemic. Bongkasa Pertiwi village can also provide a rest area for cyclists to relax while drinking coffee and breakfast with porridge typical of Bongkasa Pertiwi Village. Traditional Architecture and house conservation, organic farming and agriculture application, and cultural preservation, those can be developed for the purposes of further research objects targeting academics, such as students, lecturers, and researchers. The development of a good network can indirectly increase the opportunities for outsiders to come to visit Bongkasa Pertiwi Village. In principle, the longer they stay in the village, the more they spend money within the village environment (Hall, 2000).

Some newborn activities can be optimized as tourism potential and a form of resilience to face the pandemic. no matter how small the activity resulting from the village community's resilience process, it becomes a good opportunity to be developed into an interesting sequence of tourism activities.

1.3. Post-Pandemic Recovery: Reimagine Bongkasa Pertiwi Tourism Village

Recovery is attributed to anticipation and preparedness from "shocks", both expected and unexpected, which results from political crises, sanitary disaster, terrorist attacks, economy and the blurring effect on tourist behavior (Paraskevas et al., 2013). The tourism recovery in Bongkasa Pertiwi Village is carried out by re-arranging and transforming so that the tourism village could face the threats, both threats during the pandemic, and threats in the future. The arrangement is carried out by utilizing the existence of new-born activities as tourism potential to be developed into more resilient Special Interest Tourism activities in order to increase people's interest in travel to Bongkasa Pertiwi village. Travel interests or tourism needs were highly related to special interest tours (SIT). SIT is main attraction of tourism activities that related to culture, history, ecotourism, and tourism villages, SIT are tourism activities that driven by 6 (six) motives : 1) Novelty Seeking; 2)

Quality Seeking; 3) Rewarding; 4) Enriching; 5) Adventuring; and 6) Learning (Widhiarini, et al., 2019). Novelty seeking was tourism activities that were driven by intention on seeking something unique. Quality seeking is tourism activities that seek quality experience. Rewarding is appreciation of an object and tourist attraction visited. Enrichment is related to tourism activities that give knowledge enrichment. Adventure is a tourist activity related to the experience of adventure, usually nature expeditions, and the others. Learning is participation in tourism activities that contain educational features. Regarding the six drivers of interest in SIT mentioned above, new and existing activities in Bongkasa Pertiwi Village can be visualized as having potential as SIT in the future. The potentials that arise from new-born activities (NBA), both of which are mostly related to gastronomy (food), or the development of other activities that can collaborate with each other to form an interesting activity journey sequence that can extend visitors' time to stay long in Bongkasa Pertiwi Village.

Tourism enterprise is characterized through a dependence at the presence and functioning of companies and companies from numerous financial sectors, which might be concerned to various levels withinside the tourism industry. In order for tourism offer to emerge, tourism assets have to be available, in addition, call for for a specific tourism useful resource have to be generated, sports for the formation of the tourism product have to be regulated and stimulated, and the tourism product have to be correctly marketed (Nesterchuk et al., 2021). New-born and existing tourism activities in Bongkasa Pertiwi Village that have been recorded can be seen as a potential to create a new strategy regarding tourism resilience during pandemic time. The total number of 34 (thirtyfour) tourism activities (Existing and Newborn) in Bongkasa Pertiwi should be categorized to provide tourism needs for the right target, which at this pandemic time can only rely on local or domestic tourists. In the post-pandemic recovery stage, Bongkasa Pertiwi Tourism Village could be reorganized by analyzing tourism activities (both existing and new-born) by considering SIT motives as tools to complement qualitative approaches in this identification.

Table 4. Special Interest Tourism (SIT) Motives Analysis on Tourism Activity Categories

No	Object/Activities	Type Of Services	Tourism Activity Categories	Special Interest Tourism (Sit) Motives					
				1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Bali Swing	Tourist Rides	Man-made Attraction						
2	Sky Swing Bali	Tourist Rides	Man-made Attraction						
3	Pertiwi Quad Adventure	Rafting	Man-made Attraction						
4	Yellow Garden Rafting	Rafting	Man-made Attraction						
5	Paintball Bali Pertiwi	Shooting	Man-made Attraction						
6	Buk Dita/ Desak Nyoman Murtini	Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism						
7	Men Ranik/Ni Made Indrayani	Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism						
8	Mek Osin/Ni Wayan Wardani	Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism						

9	Anak Agung Maha Laksmi Dewi	Traditional Snacks (Godoh/Fried Banana)	Culinary Tourism						
10	Men Devi/ Ni Made Kariyanti	Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism						
11	Agung Nyoman/ I Gst. Ag. Ayu Nyoman	Porridge	Culinary Tourism						
12	Mek Armini/Ni Wayan Armini	Porridge	Culinary Tourism						
13	Men Rai/Ni Made Lodri	Porridge and Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism						
14	Men Saren/Ni Nyoman Sri Adnyani	Porridge and Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism						
15	Men Pina/Ni Ketut Aryani	Porridge and Traditional Snacks	Culinary Tourism						
16	Mek Anik/Ni Ketut Nami	Porridge and Traditional Snacks (Laklak)	Culinary Tourism						
17	Men Tawa/ Ni Nyoman Artini	Porridge and Traditional Snacks (Laklak)	Culinary Tourism						
18	Dong Sangklib/Ni Made Tomog	Porridge and Traditional Snacks (Laklak)	Culinary Tourism						
19	Buk Sika/Ni Wayan Rimin	Culinary	Culinary Tourism						
20	Airy Ubud Dewi Saraswati	Villa	Lodging						
21	Candra Loka Villa	Villa	Lodging						
22	Amara Giri Villa	Villa	Lodging						
23	Nalar House Jungle View	Villa	Lodging						
24	Pondok Mesari	Villa	Lodging						
25	Pramana Private House Rice Field View	Villa	Lodging						
26	Villa Manis 2 Bedroom Private Pool View	Villa	Lodging						
27	Pupuk Cair Wanita Tani "Manik Pertiwi" (Liquid Fertilizer)	Farming	Agrotourism						
28	Pupuk Kompos Wanita Tani "Manik Pertiwi (Compost)	Farming	Agrotourism						

29	Honey Farmer Kele-Kele Sarining Trigona Pertiwi	Farming/Livestock	Agrotourism						
30	Ngaben Massal Ceremony	Cultural	Cultural Tourism						
31	Silver Class By Pak Melan	Private Lessons	Cultural Tourism						
32	Sri Rahayu Silver	silver craft	Artshop						
33	Kerajinan Tas Daur Ulang Eco Pertiwi	Eco-handcraft	Recycled Product						
34	Yellow Garden Waste Bank	Collecting solid waste	Environment Educational Tourism						

Regarding Table 3 and 4, explains the emergence of a number of newborn activities due to the pandemic situation (newborn activities), and most of these newborn activities are tourism activities in the category of culinary tourism, agriculture or agro-tourism, or environmental education tourism. They choose businesses that target many levels of society. Culinary tourism presents the sensation of a different breakfast experience, enriches culinary knowledge indirectly, and has the opportunity to develop tourism programs that invite visitors to participate in the manufacturing process. Agrotourism provides visitors with a different and unique experience from farming and livestock. This activity category has the opportunity to provide knowledge enrichment and participate directly to learn the educational features contained in its activities. The emergence of other new categories, like recycled products and environmental education tourism, also provides a more varied choice of tourist activities for visitors who come to Bongkasa Pertiwi Village. This category is full of information to enrich knowledge, appreciate the environment, and even take part in activities related to recycling products and environment preservation. Based on the results of the analysis of the identification of tourism categories above, it can be concluded that Bongkasa Pertiwi Tourism Village has the potential as Special Interest Tourism in the post recovery phase because some activity categories already have at least 2 indicators of special interest tourism motives, so that the opportunity for Bongkasa Pertiwi Village to become resilient tourism village could be even better.

In addition, the natural and cultural conditions of the Bongkasa Pertiwi village, both tangible and intangible, also naturally attract visitors to carry out activities that attract adventure, novelty, and appreciation. Encouraged to appreciate the nature and culture of the people there. Its innovative combination produces uniqueness that fulfills the search for novelty motives and the search for quality for foreign tourists. Besides that, the natural and cultural conditions of Bongkasa Pertiwi village, both tangible and intangible, also naturally attract visitors to come to do adventurous, novelty, and rewarding activities. Encouraged to appreciate the nature and culture of the people there. The innovative combination of potentials and new activities that have emerged in Bongkasa Pertiwi village can also create a uniqueness that fulfills the novelty seeking and quality seeking motives that encourage foreign tourists to visit the village

4. Conclusion

This study explains the emergence of a number of new-born activities due to the pandemic situation, and most of these newborn activities are tourism activities in the category of culinary

tourism, agriculture or agro-tourism, or environmental education tourism. These Several local new-born activities can be optimized for tourism potential as a form of resilience to face the pandemic. No matter how small, it becomes a good opportunity to be developed into an interesting tourism activity based on SIT analysis. It seems like the crisis and pandemic did not undermine the enthusiasm of Bongkasa Pertiwi Villagers to provide people's needs for tourism even when the Pandemic was over.

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References

- Baraero-Era, J. S., & Rosario, J. D. (2020, June 15). Examining Tourism Resilience Practices as Basis for a Post-Covid 19 Recovery in the Philippines. *ASEAN journal on Hospitality and Tourism*, 18(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.5614/ajht.2020.18.1.0>
- Badung, P., 2010. *Peraturan Daerah Bupati Badung Nomor 47 Tahun 2010*, Mangupura: s.n.
- UNWTO, 2020. <http://www.unwto.org/impact-assessment-of-the-covid-19-outbreak-on-international-tourism>. [Online]
Available at: <http://www.unwto.org/impact-assessment-of-the-covid-19-outbreak-on-international-tourism>
- Frazier, T.G.; Thompson, C.M.; Dezzani, R.J.; Butsick, D. *Appl. Geogr.* 2013. *Spatial and temporal quantification of resilience at the community scale*, 42, 95–107. [CrossRef]
- Gegung, E. M., 2021. International Tourism and The Covid-19 Pandemic : The Use of Virtual Reality to Increase Tourism Destination Sustainability and How Users Perceive The Authenticity of VR Experiences. *Jurnal Kepariwisata Indonesia* 15 (1) DOI : <https://doi.org/10.47608/jki.v15i12021.9-15>, pp. 9-15.
- Hall, Collin Michael. 2000. *Tourism Planning: Policies, Processes, and Relationships*. United States:Prentice Hall.
- Litman, T., 2021. *Pandemic-Resilient Community Planning : Practical Ways to Help Communities Prepare for, Respond to, and Recover from Pandemics and Other Economic, Social and Environmental Shocks*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.vtpi.org/PRCP.pdf>
- Nesterchuck, I., Osipchuck, A., Bondarenko, E., Trusij, O., Ivanenko, V., & Chyzhevskaya, L. (2021). Reloading of Gastronomy Tours in the Conditions of Using the Right-Bank Polisia Gastronomy Potential. *GeoJournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 34(1), 170-176. <https://doi.org/10.308912/gtg.34122-633>.
- Paraskeva, Altinay, McLean & Cooper, (2013). Crisis Knowledge in Tourism: Types, Flows, and Governance, *Annals of Tourism Research*, 41, 130-152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2012.12.005>
- Rescia, A.J.; Willaarts, B.A.; Schmitz, M.F.; Aguilera, P.A. 2010. *Changes in land uses and management in two Nature Reserves in Spain: Evaluating the social-ecological resilience of cultural landscapes*. *Landsc. Urban Plan.* 98, 26–35. [CrossRef]
- Widhiarini, N. M. A. N., Oktaviani, P. E. & Permanita, N. P. F. D., 2019. Arsitektur Tradisional; Bali Pada bangunan Puri Sebagai Daya Tarik Wisata Minat Khusus Dalam Mendukung Pengembangan Pariwisata Berkelanjutan. *PUSAKA: Journal of Tourism, Hospitality, Travel and Business Event Vol.1, No.2 DOI : https://doi.org/10.33649/pusaka.v1i2.18*, pp. 46-52.